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ICT LEGISLATION IN EDUCATION AND THE USE OF ICT IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to discuss the legislation that addresses the use of information and communication technologies in education and the use of these TICs in elementary school. We verified the use of technology in our daily lives, and we also observed that this use has already expanded into schools, but we know that there are advantages and difficulties regarding its use. In addition, we sought to know, in this study, which laws address the use of these TICs in education. For this, we opted for a documentary and bibliographic study, with a search for the most recent literature and renowned authors who address the topic, using a qualitative approach with document analysis based on Cellard (2008). In the results, it was possible to highlight some legislation that had greater prominence regarding the use of TICs. It was also possible to know the main obstacles faced to insert TICs in schools, such as: difficulties for teachers, physical structure, maintenance of equipment. In addition, we highlight the advantages of using ICTs, such as improved teaching and learning, easier class planning by teachers, more creative and dynamic classes, closer relations between people and the possibility of educating regardless of place. We conclude that despite all the barriers presented, the advantages are very beneficial and provide a breadth in the student's view of the world.

Keywords— Education. Legislation. TICs

INTRODUCTION

From globalization, a great technological advance in all areas of knowledge has been observed in the world. Likewise, this technological advance has also been observed in the area of education, what we call Information and Education Technology - ICTs, which play an increasingly important role in the way we communicate, learn and live.

These are defined as a group of technologies that assist in communication, including hardware, such as smartphones and microcomputers, software, with messaging or teleconferencing applications, and everything else that can be accessed through data access networks, such as the internet. .

The use of information technology can be verified in our daily lives, being increasingly present and people increasingly dependent on them. Today, almost everyone has access to a cell phone or a computer. Therefore, this technological innovation provides the use of modern teaching resources at school, aiming at improving teaching and learning.

This progress in information technologies allowed the creation of tools that can be used by teachers in the classroom, providing greater availability of information and resources for the educator, promoting a more dynamic, efficient and innovative educational process. Therefore, the use of these technological tools in education must be understood as a new teaching methodology, which allows greater digital interaction between the educator and the student.

In addition, the arrival of ICTs in schools generated great advantages for the teaching and learning of students, but also brought several challenges in relation to their use.

However, for the use of these technologies in schools, there was the creation of a legal apparatus for their regulation, such as several laws, decrees, resolutions, among others.

RESEARCH METHOD

Thus, the step to be taken was the choice of the theme that addresses Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in education,

the next step was the planning for carrying out the research that was elaborated through the research project.

The present study focuses on the investigation of ICTs in education, thus using a qualitative approach.

As for the type of research, it will use a qualitative approach, which according to Guerra (2014) takes into account that human beings are not passive and continually interpret the world in which they live. In this way, the qualitative study has as its objective the human being.

Thus, the research will have a qualitative approach of an exploratory nature, as it aims to provide more information on the subject to be investigated.

According to Selltiz et al. (1987), this type of study includes those that aim to discover ideas and intuitions, in an attempt to acquire greater familiarity with the researched phenomenon. In this type of study there is no need to formulate hypotheses.

The techniques chosen for the collection of data used the bibliographical research where the search for the literature that approaches the ICTs in the practice of the education was made, where it was looked for the reality of the use of the ICTs in the schools, in its daily life, verifying its advantages and its difficulties.

Another technique chosen was document analysis. In the documental analysis, documents related to legislation that address the use of ICTs, including those aimed at education, were sought.

The same technique was performed using the search for literature relevant to the topic, ICTs in education, with a search on scientific literature search sites: Scielo, Google Scholar, Capes Periodical.

SEARCH RESULTS

In Brazilian Constitutional Law, it is possible to identify a reference regarding education and technology. Since education is a fundamental social right, guaranteed in arts. 6 and 205 of the Magna Carta. However, we also verified that the

constitution stipulates that the National Education Plan must articulate the national education system, through collaborative means, through integrated actions of the public authorities that lead to the humanistic, scientific and technological promotion of the Country (CF, art. 214, V).

However, it was in Law 9394/1996, the Law of Guidelines and Bases for National Education, that the use of Information and Communication Technologies in education was highlighted. LDBEN establishes the guidelines and bases of national education.

Article 32 of LDBEN (Law 9394/1996) defines the objectives of Brazilian Elementary Education, which is the basic education of citizens.

I – the development of the ability to learn, having as basic means the full mastery of reading, writing and calculation;

II – understanding the natural and social environment, the political system, technology, the arts and the values on which society is based;

III – the development of learning capacity, with a view to acquiring knowledge and skills and forming attitudes and values;

IV – the strengthening of family bonds, the bonds of human solidarity and reciprocal tolerance on which social life is based. Soon after the LDBEN, in 1997, through Ordinance nº 522 of the MEC, the National Program for Informatics in Education - PROINFO was created, which sought to introduce informatics technology in the public education network, more specifically in elementary and high school.

PROINFO works together with the Educational Technology Nuclei - NTE, which are nuclei composed of professors and professionals in the area of technology and aim to train professionals to work in this technological educational field, in addition to transforming educators as multipliers of knowledge in this nucleus (BRAZIL, 1997).

Estevão and Passos (2015, p. 201) highlight the objectives of the program:

1) Improve the quality of the teaching-learning

process;

2) Enable the creation of a new cognitive ecology in school environments through adequate incorporation of new information technologies by schools;

3) To provide an education focused on scientific and technological development;

4) Educating for global citizenship in a technologically developed society

Decree 6300, which provides for PROINFO, highlights that its main objectives are:

a) the promotion of the pedagogical use of information and communication technologies in basic education schools in urban and rural public education networks;

b) fostering the improvement of the teaching and learning process, with the use of technologies;

c) training of educational agents involved in the Program's actions (BRASIL, 2007, p. 1).

The counterpart of local governments (municipalities and state governments) for joining the program is to provide the infrastructure for schools, which is essential for them to receive computers.

Figure 1 - Institutional and organizational design of ProInfo.

Source: Estevão e Passos (2015).

Basniak and Soares (2016) state that, despite the implementation of ProInfo, it was implemented more than twenty years ago, helping in the distribution of equipment to public schools, in

training, and having led teachers to reflect on their pedagogical practice and the need for change, effective digital inclusion in the school environment has not yet been evidenced.

Also, according to Oliveira et al. (2009) the training provided by ProInfo has been providing a rethinking of teachers regarding pedagogical practice. The authors observed these transformations through the Introduction to Digital Education course, where new paths were traced in order to favor digital inclusion, thus improving the dynamics regarding the use of Educational Informatics Laboratories.

Alonso (2010) highlights that distance education is considered a teaching modality that allows for an increase in number and possibilities of access to education for an increasing portion of the population.

Maddalena comments on the growth of distance education and its regulation in terms of higher education.

[...] it can be said that the modality grew faster than its regulation and as a consequence, today we have courses and some higher education proposals that do not follow the fundamental and essential bases of Public Universities, currently there are many courses that respond to market interests and international organizations that do not bring quality proposals and are often not in line with our Latin American reality. (MADDALENA, 2012, p.1)

However, all this technological advance that invaded the world community did not occur in an integral and homogeneous way. There are still individuals who do not fully participate in this new scenario and still live on the margins of social practices carried out by digital means.

Moran (2009) highlights other problems related to this technological change at school, as he states that many schools present themselves more in a traditional than innovative way in relation to school culture. The author also states that teacher-focused teaching is still predominant, rather than a focus on teaching and learning.

This adequate management for the use of ICTs

is an important fact that is usually pointed out by teachers, mainly from public schools, as there are usually technologies available in the school, however, they lack maintenance or internet to allow access to students. contents.

Rendimento educacional - Brasil

Aprendizado dos alunos no ensino remoto com relação ao esperado no presencial*

Engajamento dos alunos da rede estadual no ensino médio remoto em 2020

*Independentemente da idade e da série.
Fonte: Insper e Instituto Unibanco

Source: <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/infomaterias/2021/07/pandemia-acentua-deficit-educacional-e-exige-aco-es-do-poder-publico#gallery-1>

According to UNESCO, in March 2021, a year after the beginning of the pandemic, almost half of the students in the world feel affected by the partial or total closure of schools, and they still estimate that more than 100 million extra children will be proficient in reading. below the minimum level as a result of this health emergency. Given this scenario, it is necessary to prioritize the recovery of Education, in order to avoid a catastrophe that will affect this entire generation.

Jovens que já pensaram em desistir dos estudos durante a pandemia

Distribuição por faixa etária em 2020

Distribuição por faixa etária em 2021

Source: <https://www12.senado.leg.br/noticias/infomaterias/2021/07/pandemia-acentua-deficit-educacional-e-exige-acoes-do-poder-publico#gallery-1>

Research shows that education and income go hand in hand. Thus, this drop in learning indicators may result in great financial loss in the near future, for students and for Brazil, as recognized by the Federal Government.

The pandemic scenario brought reflections and concerns to the educational area, as Martins (2020, p. 251) addresses “[...] the working conditions of teachers, the quality of the teaching-learning process, the relevance and meaning of topics to be addressed, the development of student-centered pedagogical practices [...]”. With this, there is a need to give voice to teachers of regular Basic Education classrooms, in order to understand their perception of the pandemic moment in relation to education and the challenges to their pedagogical practice.

CONCLUSION

The present study addressed the legislation regarding Information and Communication Technologies in schools, also highlighting the obstacles regarding its implementation and the advantages regarding its use in schools.

It was possible to know the main laws that address ICTs in education, where the mention of the theme can be observed from the Magna letter that mentions the creation of a fair society entering the scientific and technological incentive, the LDBEN that highlights that education must promote the preparation of the student and his qualification for work, since today we live in a technological environment on a daily basis. We commented on the Proinfo program that sought to introduce IT technology into the public education network, We approached the legislation that institutes EAD-type education and finally we cite Resolution No. that we live

We highlight the main obstacles to the integration of ICTs in education, where we can mention the difficulty of assimilating technologies by locations, age group, the difficulty of adapting the teacher, thus requiring continued education on the subject, the lack of maintenance of equipment in schools, the lack of internet, the constant change in technology,

the constant volume of data on the internet and the resignification of the teacher's role in the face of technology.

It was also possible to identify that the pandemic period promoted a hastily apprehension of ICTs by schools, but this did not occur in an integral way, since several schools did not resume activities, due to various obstacles.

We point out the advantages of including ICTs in schools as new ways of learning, facilitating the planning of activities, making classes more dynamic and creative for students, providing new means of interaction, also providing greater access to information, greater social interaction and allows the reduction of prejudice. We also point out the advantages in relation to EAD teaching that allows education to go beyond the walls of the school, allowing the student to have access to education anywhere, just by having access to the internet.

In addition to this range of advantages, the fact that ICTs promotes more cooperative learning is also highlighted, making thinking more critical and creative, inducing the student to meet new patterns of relationship, challenge rules and promote innovation and distinction.

We also verified that the emergency remote teaching that has been used in the pandemic period we are experiencing, allowed the continuity of school education, for the schools that joined it.

But we emphasize that the use of ICTs helps in promoting a more democratic school and promoting transformative actions that allow the student to see the world beyond the walls of the school.

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